

Co-simulation Workflow for D-Band Power Amplifier Linearization using Walsh-based DPD

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Abstract—Millimeter-wave bands open new bands of interest for ultra-high-speed wireless communications, but face technological bottlenecks such as power amplification. Working near the maximum oscillation frequency of the transistor leads to low intrinsic gain and low efficiency. Digital predistortion (DPD) achieves a higher power efficiency without degrading linearity. This paper presents a co-simulation workflow to design jointly DPD and the power amplifier (PA) in order to reach the optimum performances in linearity and power-added efficiency (PAE). The design of a PA at a center frequency of 142 GHz using the CMOS 28nm FDSOI technology from STMicroelectronics demonstrates how the design flow can take into account continuous wave (CW) and modulated signal simulations with and without DPD. The linearity performance is highlighted on the adjacent channel power ratio (ACPR) with an improvement of 4dB on an OFDM signal with 800 MHz bandwidth.

Index Terms—Co-simulation; D-Band; CMOS Power Amplifier (PA); sub-terahertz (sub-THz); digital predistortion (DPD); Walsh theory

I. INTRODUCTION

The higher part of the millimeter wave (mmW) spectrum [150 GHz-300 GHz] and terahertz [0.3 THz-3 THz] bands are investigated for new applications, encompassing high-speed communications, high-resolution sensing and spectroscopy. The D-Band [110 GHz-170 GHz] is suitable for high-speed communications thanks to its high carrier frequency and wide available spectrum. CMOS technology has been widely used in numerous works [1]–[4] as the most suitable for the mass market. However, the power gain available from each transistor is low due to its operating frequency being close to its maximum oscillation frequency (f_{max}). Thus, the output power is low and the power consumption is high, leading to poor efficiency of the overall architecture. [5] demonstrates that efficiency can drop from an average of 30% for a power amplifier (PA) around 30 GHz to 10-15% in the D-band.

The design of the PA requires a trade-off in linearity and efficiency. The linearity has directly linked to error vector magnitude (EVM) performances, but the higher it is, the lower efficiency is whereas D-Band already struggles with it. Digital predistortion (DPD) increases the linearity without damaging the power-added efficiency (PAE). The DPD is digital by nature, while the PA design is analog. It is essential to consider both linearity and PAE during the design process and to conduct comprehensive simulations of complex modulated signals at high frequencies to achieve the targeted performance. Traditional techniques for co-designing and co-simulating DPD and PA often prove time-consuming and

involve multiple steps in various formats, making them less user-friendly.

This paper demonstrates a co-simulation workflow for the design of a D-Band PA using a Walsh-based DPD. Section II overviews the PA's non-linearities characterized by memory effects and non-linear behavior. Section III presents the co-simulation workflow interfacing ADS, MATLAB, and Cadence to implement the Walsh-based DPD algorithm and to evaluate it on extracted view on Cadence. Section IV presents the design and the post-layout simulations (PLS) of the proposed architecture with and without the pre-distortion algorithm, highlighting the benefits of the DPD on modulated signal simulations. Section V concludes the paper.

II. NON-LINEARITIES AND PRE-DISTORTION IN CMOS POWER AMPLIFIER

A. Non-linearities in CMOS Power Amplifier

Complex and high-order modulations carry out signals with a high Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR). They are sensitive to the non-linearities and memory effects introduced by the PA. These effects distort the amplitude and phase leading to asymmetric spectral regrowth in adjacent communication channels. The memory effect indicates a shift in the PA's behavior resulting from previous signals that have passed through it. The performances are degraded even within the linear region at low input power, especially in wideband systems. This phenomenon is primarily caused by thermal effects (self-heating) [6] and baseband impedance effects [7] for CMOS technologies. Fig. 1 highlights the AM-AM curve of a Doherty PA driven by 100 MHz OFDM signal [8].

Fig. 1. AM-AM of a Doherty PA demonstrating a strong non-linearity and memory effect.

It exhibits a strong non-linearity phenomenon for high input powers while the memory effect predominates at low input powers.

B. Digital predistortion

Feedforward structure [9] or linear amplification with non-linear components [10] has been employed to linearize PA. However, they entail a considerable increase in cost due to a wider circuit area. The interest in DPD has gained in popularity because of its reduced cost and size. A baseband predistortion compensates the non-linearities ahead of the PA including the real-time variations inherent in integrated circuits (IC). [11] and [12] highlight the benefits of DPD in mmW beamforming systems. Fig. 2 shows the setup used for the DPD improvement characterization in a 4-element array. The process is based on iterative measurements. The output signal of the array is processed in MATLAB to recalculate the predistorter signal.

Most of the work proposes to highlight the benefits of DPD with IC measurements. However, the integration of performances achieved by the linearized system could be considered as a tool for the designer. If the PA performs sufficient EVM for the standard, optimization of saturation output power (P_{sat}), bandwidth, or PAE can be considered.

III. DIGITAL PREDISTORTION AND CO-SIMULATION WORKFLOW

A. Walsh-based digital predistortion

Inherent memory effects [13] are more pronounced when the signal exhibits a high PAPR (~ 12 dB) [14], leading to a significant increase in adjacent channel power ratio (ACPR) and EVM. The DPD compensates the non-linear effects and enables the PA to operate at its optimal PAE. [15] details an algorithm based on a Walsh block Least Mean Squares (WLMS) depicted in Fig. 3. WLMS algorithm combines the convergence properties of an overlap-save block-based LMS algorithm with the Walsh Transform to reduce its computational complexity. Thus, it exhibits a lower complexity and a faster convergence speed. An adaptive filtering or least squares method is used to identify a Memory Polynomial predistorter. The estimated gradient of the squared error is computed as an average of the data instead of its instantaneous value as in the scalar time domain approach. Therefore, it is a more accurate representation of the true gradient.

Fig. 2. DPD measurement setup [11].

Fig. 3. WLMS block diagram.

B. Co-simulation workflow

The DPD algorithm is performed in MATLAB, while the PA is designed in Cadence. A methodology is proposed to simulate jointly the DPD algorithm on the designed PA. ADS is used as a gateway between MATLAB and Cadence to control and automatize the iterative simulation for a complete system study. Fig. 4 shows the different paths between MATLAB, Cadence, and ADS.

RFIC Dynamic Link tools provided by ADS [16] enable the import of the IC model from Cadence to ADS with the same small and large signal behavior. Once the behavior of the IC is verified for continuous wave (CW) simulation, the DPD algorithm is imported from MATLAB to ADS. ADS toolboxes enable the import and link to MATLAB supporting the DPD algorithm to find the model of the PA and compensate for the non-linear effect.

IV. DESIGN AND MODULATED SIGNAL SIMULATIONS OF A D-BAND POWER AMPLIFIER

A. Schematic and layout of the Power Amplifier

A 3-stage differential PA architecture is chosen with each stage composed of a neutralized differential pair, as depicted in Fig. 5. The first stage is called the gain stage and is based on $W_1 = 20\mu m$, the second stage is the driver stage and is based on $W_2 = 40\mu m$, the last stage is the power stage and is

Fig. 4. MATLAB-ADS-Cadence co-simulation workflow.

Fig. 5. Schematic of the proposed Power Amplifier.

based on $W_3 = 80\mu m$. The gate length is equal to $L = 30nm$ for all transistors.

In each stage, two neutralization capacitances (C_n) are used to stabilize the differential pair for lower-frequency applications. However, it can also help to increase the maximum available gain (MAG) of the stage [17]–[19]. Input and output matching is performed using baluns that enable impedance matching and execute a single-to-differential signal conversion. Particular attention has been paid to input and output matching by directly integrating the RF pads within the matching networks. Inter-stage matching networks are based on transformers made up of two mutually coupled resonators (MCR) [20]. Both resonators are designed considering the input and output impedance of the different stages. The transformer achieves wideband matching without adding too many losses.

The layout is displayed in Fig. 6. The die area is $1180\mu m \times 770\mu m$ with a core area of $400\mu m \times 770\mu m$. All simulations presented in the following are performed on the entire circuit, considering all the interconnections, ground-plane interactions, and transistors.

B. Post Layout Simulations

S-Parameters simulations are performed from 100 GHz to 200 GHz , covering the D-Band. The maximum small signal gain is obtained at $f = 142\text{ GHz}$ with $S_{21max} = 15.5\text{ dB}$. The 3 dB bandwidth is 24 GHz from 131 GHz to 155 GHz . The input and output reflection coefficients of, respectively, -9.6 dB and -10.4 dB at 142 GHz .

Fig. 7 shows the frequency behavior in PAE, in saturation output power (P_{sat}), and in power gain from 138 GHz to 164 GHz . Fig. 8 shows the best in-band performances achieved at 142 GHz to highlight PAE performances and 1 dB output compression point (OC_{P1dB}). The large signal frequency behavior shows a maximum gain of 15.5 dB at 142 GHz , correlated with small-signal simulations, and with a maximum PAE of 10.7% . The P_{sat} is between 7.5 dBm and

Fig. 6. Layout view of the 3-Stage Power Amplifier.

Fig. 7. PAE, P_{sat} , and power gain results for the 138 GHz-164 GHz Band.

Fig. 8. Continuous Wave characterization of the PA at 142 GHz .

10 dBm over the 130 GHz - 160 GHz band. Maximum performance is achieved at 142 GHz . Output saturation power is 9.7 dBm with a power gain of 15.5 dB and a peak PAE of 10.7% . The OC_{P1dB} is 5.4 dBm . These performances are summarized in Table I. It shows that the achieved performances are in line with other architectures seen in State-of-the-Art.

C. Modulated signal simulations considering the DPD

Modulated signal simulations are performed to compare the PA behavior with and without DPD. The input modulated signal is based on the following scenario: a 64-QAM OFDM with 800 MHz bandwidth and -11 dBm of average power. Fig. 9 shows the AM/AM improvement with respect to memory effects. The impact of DPD becomes noticeably visible, especially in reducing memory effects in the linear region of the PA. Based on this calculated model, a predistorted signal is created to improve the ACPR. Fig. 10 shows the output spectrum obtained, with and without DPD.

The ACPR is measured for the upper and lower band around the center frequency. On the lower band, the ACPR decreased from -34.59 dBc to -38.37 dBc , and on the upper band, it decreased from -34.5 dBc to -38.2 dBc . The overall improvement on ACPR is 4 dB for both bands. Also, linearization increases OC_{P1dB} from 5.4 dBm to 5.8 dBm . As a comparison, the same levels of ACPR are obtained for non-linearized PA with an average input power of -13.6 dBm .

TABLE I
STATE-OF-THE-ART FOR D-BAND ARCHITECTURE.

	[20]	[21]	[22]	[23]	[24]	[25]	This work
Process	28nm CMOS	65nm CMOS	65nm CMOS	45nm CMOS SOI	65nm CMOS	65nm CMOS	28nm FDSOI
f_{max} [GHz]	N.A*	250	250	270	289	250	310
Operation frequency [GHz]	135	150	118	140	150	150	142
Gain [dB]	21.9	19.2	22.3	22.2	17.5	22	15.5
P_{sat} [dBm]	11.8	N.A*	14.5	16	9.4	N.A*	9.6
3 dB BW [GHz]	20	14	17	21	5	9	24
Peak PAE [%]	10.7	N.A*	10.2	12.5	13.3	N.A*	10.7
Core Area [mm^2]	0.24	0.6	0.343	0.43	0.202	0.4	0.32

Fig. 9. AM/AM Characteristics of the PA with and without DPD.

Fig. 10. Output Spectrum of the PA before and after applying DPD algorithm.

The workflow has demonstrated its efficiency by providing a large set of simulations to secure the design:

- The IC designer focuses on primary constraints for D-Band design targeting first the bandwidth, the P_{sat} , and the efficiency.
- The co-simulation carries out the linearity improvements to check compliance with the standard requirements.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a co-simulation workflow between ADS, MATLAB, and Cadence to simulate a D-Band PA using a Walsh-based DPD. The performances are in line with the

State-of-the-Art displaying a gain of 15.5 dB and a PAE up to 10.7% at 142 GHz. The workflow carries out modulated signal simulations to quantify exhaustively the benefits of DPD with an ACPR improvement of 4 dB and an $OCPI_{dB}$ of 0.4dB on an 800 MHz 64-QAM OFDM signal with a carrier of 142 GHz.

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